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UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA INTERFAOL METODLAR YORDAMIDA INGLIZ TILI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH YO'LLARI

D. A. Mirsagatov

Target International School O'quv ishlar bo'yicha bo'lim boshlig'i

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada interfaol o'qitish metodlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, shuningdek, o'qituvchi va ta'lim oluvchining maqsaddan natijaga erishishida metodlarni tanlay olish mahoratlari haqidagi masalalar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interfaol metod, Bumerang, baholash tartibi, yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxs.

Abstract: This article highlights the distinctive features of interactive teaching methods, as well as the issues related to the teacher's and learner's ability to select appropriate methods to achieve their goals effectively.

Key words: interactive method, Boomerang, assessment procedure, highly moral individual.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещены особенности интерактивных методов обучения, а также вопросы, связанные с умением преподавателя и обучающегося выбирать методы для достижения поставленных целей.

Ключевые слова: интерактивный метод, Бумеранг, порядок оценивания, высоконравственная личность.

KIRISH

Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi oldiga qo'yilgan davlat va ijtimoiy buyurtmaga muvofiq, ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining samaradorligini oshirish, ilm-fanning so'nggi yutuqlarini amaliyotga joriy etish orqali ijodkor, ijtimoiy faol, yuksak ma'naviyatli, kasb-hunarli, ona-Vatanga sadoqatli, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalangan, ijodiy va mustaqil fikr yurita oladigan, davlat va jamiyat oldida o'z burchi va javobgarligini his etadigan barkamol shaxsni kamolga yetkazish kabi muhim vazifalarni amalga oshirish nazarda tutiladi¹.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Ushbu vazifalarning muvaffaqiyatli hal etilishi ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida zamonaviy interfaol metodlardan foydalanishni taqozo etadi.

O'quv-tarbiya jarayonida o'quvchilarni ijodiy fikrlashga, o'zgaruvchan vaziyatlarga moslashishga o'rgatish, erkin raqobat asosida faoliyatni tashkil etish, shuningdek, ularning amaliy mashg'ulotlarda axborot texnologiyalari, elektron darsliklar, versiyalar va multimedialardan foydalana olish qobiliyatini shakllantirish muhimdir. Bu esa o'quvchilarda mustaqillik, erkin fikrlashni tarbiyalashni, o'quv faoliyatini tahlil qilishni, istiqbolda kasbiy mahorat va kompyuter savodxonligini orttirishni ularning ichki ehtiyojiga aylantirishni talab etadi.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Zamonaviy interfaol metodlar ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining bir tizimga solingan ilmiy-nazariy va metodik asoslangan yangi shakl, usul va vositalarining majmuidir. Bunda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish samarali yechim bo'la oladi, deb o'ylaymiz. Ingliz tili darslarida interfaol o'qitish metodlaridan foydalanish qisqa vaqt ichida muayyan nazariy bilimlarni egallash, ma'lum faoliyat yuzasidan ko'nikma va malakalarni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ta'lim amaliyotida keng qo'llanilayotgan interfaol o'qitish metodlari bu jarayondagi belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirishda zarur vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

¹ F. Egamberdiyeva, M.Toshov. Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi. Toshkent-2023.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

Interfaol ingliz tilidagi “inter” – o‘zaro va “act” – harakat qilmoq ma’nolarini bildirib, ularning umumiy mazmuni interfaol – ya’ni o‘zaro harakat qilmoq ma’nosini anglatadi. Interfaol o‘qitishda o‘qituvchi o‘quv faoliyatining faol tashkilotchisi bo‘lib, ta’lim oluvchi bu faoliyatning sub’ekti sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Interfaol metodlar ta’lim oluvchilardan zaruriy axborotlarni o‘zlashtirish jarayonidagi faollik, ijodkorlik va mustaqillikni shakllantiribgina qolmay, o‘qitish maqsadlarining to‘laqonli amalga oshishiga yordam beradi².

Interfaol o‘qitish metodlarining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlaridan yana biri shundaki, unda ta’limning rejalashtirilgan maqsadiga erishishni kafolatlaydigan o‘zlashtirish jarayoni loyihalashtiriladi. O‘qituvchi va ta’lim oluvchining maqsaddan natijaga erishishida qanday metodni tanlashlari ularning ixtiyorida, chunki har ikkala tomonning asosiy maqsadi aniq – natijaga erishish. Bunda ta’lim oluvchining bilim saviyasi, guruh xarakteri va sharoitga qarab metod tanlanadi. Ingliz tili darslarida interfaol o‘qitish metodlari va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali har bir mashg‘ulotda ta’lim oluvchilarning faol va hamkorlikdagi ishtiroki ta’minlanadi. Fikrimiz dalili sifatida ingliz tili darsida “O‘zbekiston shaharlari” mavzusini o‘rganishda “Bumerang” texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodikasini keltirib o‘tamiz.

“Bumerang” texnologiyasi.

Texnologiyaning maqsadi – talabalarning tarqatma materiallardan foydalana olish va berilgan mavzu yuzasidan bahs-munozaraga kirisha olish malakasini rivojlantirish.

Texnologiyani o‘tkazish bosqichlari: talabalar 4–5 kishidan iborat kichik guruhlariga ajratiladi va har bir guruh a’zosiga mavzu yuzasidan tarqatma materiallar beriladi; guruhlariga berilgan matnni yakka tartibda alohida o‘rganish, eslab qolish va o‘zlashtirish lozim bo‘ladi. Buning uchun o‘qituvchi tomonidan 15 daqiqa vaqt belgilanadi; o‘qituvchi talabalarga tartib raqamlari yozilgan kichik qog‘ozlardan bittadan tortib olishlarini taklif etadi (guruhda 4 kishi bo‘lsa, qog‘ozdagi raqamlar 1, 2, 3, 4 bo‘ladi). Nechta guruh bo‘lsa, shuncha raqamli qog‘ozlar tayyorlanadi; raqamlar bo‘yicha talabalardan yangi guruhlar tuziladi, ya’ni 1-raqamni olganlar 1-stolga, 2-raqamni olganlar 2-stolga shu tarzda joylashadi. Har bir guruh a’zosi o‘zi bilan o‘rgangan matnni olib keladi; raqamlar bo‘yicha yangi guruhlar tuzilganda, har bir guruhda avvalgi guruhlardan bittadan vakil to‘planadi. Natijada umumiy mavzu bo‘yicha 4 tinglovchi va 4 xil matn yig‘iladi; har bir a’zo o‘zi avval o‘rgangan materialni boshqalarga tushuntiradi, izohlaydi va ularning o‘zlashtirish darajasini tekshiradi. Bu vazifa talabandan o‘qituvchi sifatida harakat qilishni talab etadi; guruh a’zolari navbatma-navbat tushuntirilayotgan matnni eshitadi, tahlil qiladi va yodda saqlashga harakat qiladi. Bu esa tinglovchi bo‘lishni talab etadi; o‘qituvchi matn hajmini inobatga olgan holda vaqt belgilaydi; guruh ishtirokchilari matn bilan tanishib bo‘lganidan so‘ng, savollar yordamida bir-birlariga mazmunni mustahkamlash bo‘yicha topshiriq beriladi. Bu jarayon o‘qituvchi tomonidan tushuntiriladi; vazifa bajarilgach, o‘qituvchi talabalarga yana avvalgi joylariga qaytib o‘tirishni taklif etadi; o‘qituvchi talabalarga istalgan savol bilan murojaat qiladi va ulardan javob oladi. So‘ng, guruh a’zolariga matndan kelib chiqqan holda savollar tuzib, boshqa guruhlariga berish topshirig‘i tushuntiriladi; amalga oshirilayotgan harakatlar diqqat bilan kuzatilib, o‘qituvchi tomonidan baholanadi; talabalarga minnatdorchilik bildiriladi va mashg‘ulot yakunlanadi³.

Misol tariqasida ingliz tili mashg‘ulotida “O‘zbekiston shaharlari” mavzusida foydalanish mumkin bo‘lgan “Bumerang” texnologiyasini o‘tkazish metodini keltiramiz.

1-guruh: Tashkent is the capital of Uzbekistan

Tashkent is the capital of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. It is a very old city. It was founded more than 2,200 years ago. The city is located at the foothills of the Tian Shan mountain range and lies in the Chirchik river valley. The population of the city has already grown to more than 2.7 million people. There are several Muslim monuments and historical buildings such as the Kukeldash Madrasah and the Barak-Khan Mosque, which were built in the 16th century. Tashkent, which has new avenues, squares, high-rise buildings and fountains, has become the most modern city in Uzbekistan. The city is flourishing as never before. The transport facilities are good. There are buses, trolleybuses, trams, rated with traditional Uzbek art. Tashkent is the educational and scientific centre of Uzbekistan, where there are a lot of universities, institutes, schools and special secondary schools. The city has the Republic’s Academy of Sciences, which unites dozens of research institutes. It is also a cultural centre with many libraries, theatres and cinemas. Tashkent’s industrial establishments, which produce cotton fabric, textile machinery, electrical equipment, cotton harvesters and other products, are well-known not only in the CIS but around the world. Tashkent is often called a city of peace and friendship. Recently, Tashkent became well-known in the world as the capital where summit talks have been held. A lot of embassies and offices of many international organizations, companies and firms have opened in the city.

2 Ishmuhamedov R. J. O‘quv jarayonida interfaol uslublar va pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo‘llash uslubiyoti. T.: 2008.

3 Shodmonova Sh, Mirsagatova N.S, Ibragimova G.N, Mirsolieva M.T. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. T.: 2011.

2-guruh: **Samarkand – the capital of tamerlane**

Samarkand is situated in the valley of the river Zarafshan. It is the second-largest city of Uzbekistan and is of the same age as the city of Babylon or Rome. The history of Samarkand is about 2,500 years old and has witnessed many upheavals during the times of Alexander the Great, the Arabic conquest, Genghis Khan's conquest and, lastly, Tamerlane's. Hence, the culture of Samarkand was developed and mixed together with Iranian, Indian, Mongolian, and a bit of Western and Eastern cultures. Majestic and beautiful city Samarkand has a marvellous and attractive power. Poets and historians of the past called it "Rome of the East", "The beauty of sublunary countries", "The pearl of the Eastern Muslim World." Its advantageous geographical position in the Zarafshan valley put Samarkand in the first place among cities of Central Asia. Over history, this legendary city on the Silk Road went through growth and decline, suffered from destructive invasions by foreign rulers and revived again, becoming even more beautiful. Trade routes to the west (Persia), to the east (China), and to the south (India) intersected here and formed intersections of the Silk Road. Today, Samarkand is the treasure of unique antiquity. It is included in the UNESCO World Heritage List due to the abundance of material and spiritual values. Unique monuments of ancient architecture, the heritage of scientific and art schools, artisans' workshops are well-known around the world.

3-guruh: **Khiva – the museum under the blue**

Khiva may be a small city – its population barely tops 40,000 – but its history as the best-preserved stop on the old Silk Road gives it a broad appeal for tourists tracing the historic trading route. Located in the Khorezm oasis of the Kara-Kum Desert, Khiva was the capital of the Khivan Khanate from 1592 until the Bolshevik takeover in 1920. Nobody seems to know exactly how old this ancient city is, though the story goes that Khiva was founded by none other than Shem, the son of Noah (of Ark fame); at the very least, the city dates back to the 7th century and probably much earlier. Despite its seemingly romantic history as a Silk Road oasis, the city became most notable as Central Asia's biggest slave trade centre. For those who've seen old cities at their best and worst, Khiva may feel a bit like the Williamsburg of the East, for its genuine dirt and din were swept clean by aggressive Soviet sanitation in the 1970s. Intent on transforming the traditionally teeming city into a living museum, Khiva was purged of much of its ancient bustle, and its buildings were scrubbed down (or, in some cases such as the 9th-century Juma Mosque, rebuilt) and turned into public exhibits. Khiva is a day-trip city – good hotels and other tourist services are in short supply – but it's a popular excursion from Urgench. Most of the city's mosques, minarets and other landmarks, renowned for their delicate majolica tiles and naturalistic paintings, are located in the historic Ichon-Qala area. Must-sees include the exquisite 19th-century Tosh-Khovli Palace, the 225-foot tall Islam Khodja Minaret, and Pahlavon Mahmud's mausoleum, with its proverb-embossed tiles honouring the great Khivan philosopher and teacher.

4-guruh: **Bukhara – a cultural gem**

Bukhara is one of the most ancient cities in Central Asia. Most of the monuments in this romantic Eastern city, which attracts tourists from all over the world, date back to the Middle Ages. Nevertheless, archaeological excavations conducted by the Uzbek Academy of Sciences (expedition led by A. Mukhamedjonov) have revealed thick cultural layers, i.e., traces of ancient settlements in locations providing favourable conditions for life. It has been established as fact that Bukhara never changed its site but grew vertically. In archaeological cross-sections of almost 20 metres, there have been discovered the remnants of dwellings, public buildings and fortifications. These have been dated on the basis of the artefacts associated with them: ceramic pottery, fireplaces, coins bearing images and inscriptions, jewellery, tools of artisans – i.e., everything associated with the activities and culture of human society. The lower layers (3rd–4th centuries B.C. to the 1st century A.D.) of the period of antiquity are the thickest. The upper layers are those of the mediaeval city (from the 9th to the beginning of the 20th centuries). This means that Bukhara is at least 2,500 years old, just like Samarkand. True, the local inhabitants are firmly convinced that their city is 3,000 years old and insist on continuation of archaeological excavations. As in the past, the people of Bukhara are fanatical patriots. Even today, Bukhara displays the layout contours of a mediaeval city. The city streets clearly define the shakhristan – the historical core of Bukhara. There still remains the Ark citadel and blocks of residential buildings in the downtown section, which have been declared an architectural reserve. It is also possible to trace today the former international and local caravan routes which cut through the city walls. The city gates were named after the cities and notable places to which they led. As the city of Bukhara grew, the walls were moved concentrically, and new gates were put up along the caravan routes⁴.

⁴ Bukhara a museum in the open. T.: Gafur Gulyam Art and Literature Publishers, 1991.

Baholash tartibi:

Berilgan savollarga to'liq javob bo'lsa – 3 ball, qo'shimcha qilinsa – 2 ball, o'tirgan joyidan fikr bildirsa – 1 ball, javob bermasa – 0 ball bilan belgilanadi.

Ingiliz tili darslarida “Bumerang” texnologiyasidan foydalanish nafaqat ta'lim oluvchilarni mavzuni qisqa vaqt ichida o'qib tushunish yoki u yuzasidan bahs-munozara olib borishga, balki ishtirokchilarning darsdagi faoliyatini ham baholashga o'rgatadi. Bugunning dolzarb muammolaridan biri ta'lim tizimi sifatini yaxshilash va o'quvchilarga sifatli ta'lim berishdir. Buning uchun pedagoglardan interfaol metodlardan unumli foydalanish, to'g'ri tanlov qilish va o'quvchilarda qiziqish uyg'otish talab etiladi. Shu bilan birga, pedagog ko'proq o'z ustida ishlashi, yangi interfaol metodlarni izlab topishi asosiy masalalardan biri bo'lib hisoblanadi⁵.

XULOSA

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, pedagoglar tomonidan dars loyihasini ishlab chiqish va olib borish jarayonlari to'g'ri tashkil etilsa, o'qituvchi va ta'lim oluvchi o'rtasidagi hamkorlik to'liq ta'minlansa, kutilgan natijaga hamda dars samarasiga erishish mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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⁵ Avlayev O.U., Jo'rayeva S.N., Mirzayeva S.P. “Ta'lim metodlari” o'quv-uslubiy qo'llanma, “Navro'z” nashriyoti, Toshkent – 2017.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №3

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